

ERICXPLORE PUBLISHERS INTERNATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGY

ERICXPLORE JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Vol 1, Issue 1 (2) Nov. 2024

Available online at: www.ericolutions.com

Influence of Emotional Disturbances on the Relationships and Careers of Women

Dr Eric Kwasi Elliason, Post Doctor of Philosophy Scholar, Kennedy University of St Lucia.

Gordon Buadi -Miezah, PhD Scholar, University of Cape Coast, Ghana

Email: manericus20172gmail.com

Introduction

Emotional disturbances in women refer to a broad range of psychological disorders, such as depression, anxiety, mood disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Women do not experience these conditions the same way. Depression and anxiety are the most prevalent mental health problems among women, with studies showing that women have nearly two times higher chances of suffering from these diseases than men (Kuehner, 2017). The prevalence of mood disorders, including bipolar disorder, is also seen to be higher in women, which contributes to the broader spectrum of emotional disturbances affecting their overall well-being (Eid et al., 2019).

Intricate biological-psychological-social factors influence the development of these emotional disturbances. The hormonal imbalance that results from puberty, the menstrual cycle, pregnancy, and menopause can have a significant impact on a woman's mood and emotional control over the course of her lifetime. These hormonal variations render females more receptive to conditions like depression or anxiety (Albert, 2015). Psychologically, females tend to internalize stress and emotional pain, thus paving the way for anxiety or depressive disorders (Nolen-Hoeksema, 2012). Socially, societal expectations, gender-based violence, and pressures resulting from work-family life

Elliason, E.K., Buadi-Miezah G. (2024). EricXplore Journal of Research and Innovation. Vol. 1. Issue 1(2). Nov. 2024

balance all contribute to females' emotional disturbances (World Health Organization [WHO], 2019).

For successful interventions and support systems, it is essential to understand the nature of these disorders and their impact on relationships. The romantic partners, family members, or friends can be sources of support or triggers for emotional disorders. For instance, managing emotional disturbances can often stress romantic ties, while good and positive relationships may help avoid such adverse situations (Whisman, 2013). As a result, dealing with women's emotional disturbances requires a comprehensive strategy, encompassing biological and psychological aspects as well as social factors.

Methods

A rigorous literature search was conducted to identify studies published between 2010 and 2024 that examined emotional problems in women and their consequent effects on relationships. Databases such as PubMed, PsycINFO, and Google Scholar were used for this search, using different keywords like "emotional disturbances in women," "impact on relationships," "depression," "anxiety," "PTSD," and "mood disorders." Inclusion criteria focused on peer-reviewed articles,

systematic reviews, and meta-analyses that provided empirical evidence. Exclusion criteria included articles that did not provide empirical data, editorials, commentaries, and opinions. Also, articles that were published later than 2010 were excluded.

Results

Emotional Disturbances in Women

The results of the research demonstrate that biological, psychological, and social factors frequently have complex influences on emotional disturbances in women. Anxiety disorders and depression are among the most common emotional problems, with studies showing women as more susceptible to these conditions than men (Kuehner, 2017). Hormonal fluctuations, significantly during menstruation, pregnancy, or menopause, can worsen these conditions (Gordon et al., 2016). Moreover, societal pressures and gender roles add up to increase the burden of emotional disturbances in women, making them more likely to become mentally ill (Nolen-Hoeksema, 2012).

Emotional disturbances in women take several forms, including depression, anxiety disorders, PTSD, and mood disorders. Each condition has its implications for the emotional wellness of

women, which result in significant personal relationship issues as well as social ones.

Depression

Depression is a widely studied emotional disturbance affecting a significant number of women, with investigations pointing at approximately twice the likelihood of major depressive disorder occurrence among women compared to men (Albert, 2015). This discrepancy in rates between genders has been associated with various factors, including biological differences, such as hormonal changes occurring during reproductive events such as menstruation and breastfeeding (Gordon et al., 2016). These hormonal imbalances in women seem to make them more at risk of developing depressive symptoms, leading them to possible episodes of depression (Kuehner, 2017).

Also, social-psychological factors play a role in the increasing rates of depression among women. Stressful life events like bereavement, separation/divorce, or money issues can cause or exacerbate depressive episodes. According to Nolen-Hoeksema (2012), women often feel more stressed than men because they are required to meet up with societal expectations and gender roles, thus increasing their chances of becoming depressed. The overlapping influences between genetic predispositions

and environmental stressors highlight the complex nature of depression in females, requiring multifaceted treatment approaches and support.

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a specific form of depression that affects women after childbirth, with an estimated prevalence of 10-15% worldwide (O'Hara & McCabe, 2013). PPD does not only affect the mother's mental health but also hampers mother-infant attachment, leading to developmental issues for the child in adulthood. The shame that comes along with postnatal depression usually makes women not seek medical intervention, making it worse (Slomian et al., 2019).

Anxiety Disorders

Anxiety disorders are another group of emotional disturbances that have more impact on females than males. These include generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), panic disorder, and social anxiety disorder. Research has identified that various factors, including biological changes, like hormonal imbalances (during reproductive events such as menstruation and breastfeeding), contribute to this increased susceptibility among women (McLean et al., 2011). Besides, menstrual cycle-related fluctuations in estrogen/progesterone have been connected with changes in anxiety levels, with

heightened anxiety (Reardon & Malik, 2021).

Additionally, societal pressure and gender-specific stressors, such as having to balance a career and family life at the same time, can exacerbate women's anxiety symptoms. Traumatic life events like sexual assault and domestic violence also contribute to the development of anxiety disorders in women (Tolin & Foa, 2006). According to Olf (2017), women are more likely to suffer from anxiety after trauma than men. This discrepancy may be due to different coping mechanisms and social support systems.

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)

Women have a higher rate of suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) compared to men, mainly due to sex-based violence such as rape, intimate partner violence, and early childhood abuse (Dworkin et al., 2017). There are twice as many women diagnosed with PTSD as men, despite men having experienced more possibly traumatic events (Olf, 2017). Interpersonal trauma involving betrayal of trust, which frequently affects women and has worse psychological repercussions, is one reason for this difference (Powers et al., 2017).

In women, those disturbances may persist chronically and can manifest themselves as feelings of fear that constantly recur, along with hyperarousal symptoms and intrusive thoughts about the trauma. These symptoms can be disastrous, making it hard for victims to function correctly in their daily lives, leading to withdrawal from social events. Others find it difficult to trust people, hence breaking relationships with loved ones or difficulties in maintaining intimacy among them (Ruglass & Kendall-Tackett, 2014).

Mood Disorders

Another critical area where many female patients need help is mood disorders, including bipolar depression, seasonal patterns, major depressive disorder, and cyclothymic disorder. Bipolar disorder is complicated for women as it often presents unique challenges in relationships due to its extreme mood swings between mania and depression. Hyperactivity, increased irritability, rapid speech, decreased need for sleep, and some grandiose behaviors are the signs that depict maniac episodes (Leahy et al., 2012).

It has also been found that compared to men with bipolar disorder, women are more likely to experience rapid cycling or mixed episodes, which further impact their relationships (Kennedy et al., 2016). Such

mood changes make it hard for the patient and her partner to maintain a stable and supportive relationship. Furthermore, many women's first experiences of bipolar disorder are linked to reproductive events like the postpartum period, thus complicating their management of the disorder (Freeman et al., 2017).

Overall, these disorders prove challenging because they are closely associated with hormone changes in women as well as psychosocial stressors.

Effects of Emotional Disturbances on Relationships

Women's emotional disturbances significantly affect different kinds of relationships, including love affairs, parent-child ties, and social interactions. These disturbances pose enormous challenges to having healthily supportive relationships, leading to several negative consequences among affected women and those around them.

Romantic Relationships

Depression, anxiety, and mood disorders are significant emotional disturbances that put much pressure on romantic relationships. Communication breakdowns, emotional distancing, and increased

conflicts are the result of these conditions, which eventually lead to relationship dissatisfaction and breakups. For example, depression in females is consistently linked with reduced satisfaction with their relationships. According to Whisman (2013), women's depressive symptoms often correlate with their dissatisfaction with their partners, leading to heightened conflict levels that may cause separation or divorce fears.

Additionally, research indicates that anxiety disorders can worsen relationship problems by promoting dependence and avoidance patterns. On the one hand, generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) in women can make them overly dependent on their partners for reassurance, thereby bringing about feelings of being suffocated and resented within a relationship (Beesdo-Baum et al., 2012). Conversely, ladies with social phobia might evade social contact with their partners, thus causing distance between them and weakening bonds (Porter & Chambless, 2014).

Moreover, there is substantial interference in romantic relationships by mood disorders such as bipolar disorder. The unpredictability of the mood swings that bipolar disordered women experience causes an intense period of attachment to follow by withdrawal and apathy, which

confuses the situation (Levy & Johnson, 2014). In most cases, family members married to women with bipolar disorders have reported helplessness as they cannot cope with rapid changes in moods as well as behaviors (Rowe & Morris, 2012).

Parent-Child Relationships

Maternal depression has been widely studied regarding its influence on parenting behavior and child outcomes. Regarding this, Goodman et al. (2011) state that depressed mothers display less responsiveness or more negativity when handling children, hence affecting them negatively and, in some cases, leading to emotional or behavioral problems. Children with depressed mothers are often deprived of the emotional support and nurturing required for proper attachment and, hence, at higher risk of developmental delays.

Anxiety disorders also cripple the mother's parenting behavior. Mothers suffering from anxiety disorders may become overprotective or controlling, stunting their children's autonomy and social development (Ginsburg et al., 2004). Furthermore, they avoid specific responsibilities that come with parenting due to their fears, thus leading to inconsistency in parenting and confusion for the child (Williams et al., 2009).

Postpartum depression (PPD) has a particularly detrimental effect on the mother-infant bond. Due to PPD, a mother may be unable to properly engage with her infant through activities such as smiling, cuddling, and playing, which are crucial for a child's emotional development. According to Field (2010), infants of depressed mothers exhibit more distress symptoms such as crying, fussiness, difficulty sleeping, etc., further stressing the mother-child relationship.

Social Relationships

Emotional disturbances among women similarly affect their social relationships, including friendships and broader networks. Women with illnesses like depression and anxiety may exhibit isolation from social interactions, which reduces the support systems available to them (Fine & Sani, 2012). Withdrawal can be both an outcome as well as a symptom of their emotional disturbance, thus leading to vicious cycles in which loneliness, anxiety, and pain get worse with isolation (Cacioppo et al., 2014).

Social withdrawal, which results in feelings of rejection or oblivion from friends and family, can also be the cause of deteriorating social relationships. The erosion of social support is one consequence that results from this, with

implications for emotional well-being and recovery from mental health issues (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Without such assistance, it will become more challenging for women to cope with their emotional struggles to reach out and seek help.

Additionally, the stigma surrounding mental illness can make social withdrawal worse. Emotional disturbances in women may make them fear that others will judge or discriminate against them, causing them to hide their challenges and avoid any form of interaction with other people. Due to this stigma, they find it difficult to open up to friends or family members as well as mental health professionals, leading to further isolation and deterioration in their emotional state (Corrigan & Watson, 2002).

Workplace Relationships

Relationships at the workplace can be affected in various ways due to emotional disturbances experienced by women, thus impacting team dynamics and individual performance. Depressed females might find it hard to communicate, hence leading them to misunderstandings, which generate difficulties when dealing with workmates and bosses. For instance, depression may cause withdrawal symptoms such as reduced motivation and lack of

involvement that may seem to be indifference or even disloyalty on the part of colleagues (Wang et al., 2014). Similarly, anxiety disorders impair interactions within job settings because sufferers tend to avoid the company of others or feel nervous during meetings, thereby affecting the cohesion among teammates (Ménard et al., 2016).

Emotional disturbances may lead to a woman not effectively participating in group work. As a result of mood fluctuations such as those observed under bipolar disorder, periods where one is highly productive are usually followed by episodes characterized by low energy levels or irritability (Leahy et al., 2012). Inadequate participation may frustrate teammates, cause divisions, and affect the overall team productivity and quality of work.

Emotional disturbances also impede professional relationships, which is detrimental to career advancement. Networking opportunities, mentorship, and advocating for oneself might be challenging for women suffering from conditions like PTSD or severe anxiety symptoms when it comes to job search (Dworkin et al., 2017). This could lead to missed chances of promotion or professional progression,

which makes them feel more useless and emotionally sick.

There is a higher possibility that workplace conflicts can occur with emotional disturbances. For example, heightened sensitivity or irritability associated with anxiety disorders may give rise to misunderstandings and arguments among colleagues that can escalate into conflicts, thereby spoiling the professional relationship (Whisman, 2013). Moreover, trying to cope with their disturbance while doing their jobs is a source of stress, resulting in burnout, loss of job satisfaction, and even absenteeism, thus leading to further depletion of any rapport between employees (Cacioppo et al., 2014).

Emotional disturbances have significant implications for women in leadership positions. Managers struggling with depression or anxiety may find it hard to make decisions, provide clear directions, or have the confidence needed to lead teams effectively. This affects subordinates and their team's overall performance and morale (Goodman et al., 2011). In addition, because mental health issues carry a stigma that discourages women from seeking help, this only worsens its negative effect on leadership ability amongst women as well as relationships at workplaces.

Multiple emotional disturbances may affect work relationships in the organization over time. Such difficulties can lead to an unhealthy work environment with low spirits, high attrition rates, and reduced job output (Whisman, 2013). Neglecting such concerns could stop these organizations from addressing the stigma surrounding mental health at workplaces, which makes affected people feel isolated and damages their relationship with colleagues.

Impact of Interventions

Psychotherapy

Extensive research has been conducted on psychotherapy, particularly cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and interpersonal therapy (IPT), which has shown that it is efficient in treating emotional disturbances such as depression and anxiety among women. CBT focuses on changing negative thoughts and behaviors that contribute to emotional distress, while IPT deals with interpersonal issues in general social functioning (Cuijpers et al., 2016). Several studies have confirmed that the two treatments can lead to significant improvements in mood, anxiety levels, and overall life quality (Cuijpers et al., 2016; Cuijpers et al., 2019). Nevertheless, access to these therapies may be restricted due to socioeconomic factors like the cost of treatment, lack of insurance coverage, or

unavailability of skilled personnel within specific geographical locations (Cuijpers et al., 2016; Olfson et al., 2017). Also, women often face much stigma when they are seeking psychotherapy because they fear showing any signs of weakness before other people (Corrigan, 2014). Again, these stereotype-based mental health misconceptions originating from different cultures can make available therapeutic resources go underutilized (Wang et al., 2007).

Pharmacotherapy

Among women with emotional disturbances, psychotherapy is commonly used, including antidepressants and anxiolytics. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) have been demonstrated to be efficacious in aiding depression and anxiety symptoms, respectively (Gartlehner et al., 2017). For managing acute symptoms of anxiety, anxiolytics like benzodiazepines are also used.

Weight gain, sexual dysfunction, or gastrointestinal problems might accompany these medications, thereby affecting adherence and overall life quality (Gartlehner et al., 2017). In addition, pharmacotherapy alone does not address the underlying psychosocial factors

responsible for emotional disturbances such as interpersonal conflicts or trauma (Cuijpers et al., 2019). This shows a limitation that indicates that psychopharmacology should be integrated with psychological treatment and other supportive interventions to come up with a comprehensive approach to care.

Support Groups

Peer support groups are an essential resource for women suffering from emotional disturbances because they can facilitate discussions about their experiences and coping mechanisms. These communities help foster relationships among women, thereby reducing isolation and offering advice and comfort to people with similar experiences (Kleiber & Lichtman, 2019). It has been argued that being involved in support group sessions improves emotional well-being, thus enhancing perceived social support (Dennis, 2003).

However, support groups may be inadequate for those women who experience more severe cases of emotional disturbances, as they may require highly intensive medical interventions (Kleiber & Lichtman, 2019). Moreover, the effectiveness of the support groups can vary according to the dynamics within the group, the abilities of facilitators, and how open

participants are during interactions (Yalom & Leszcz, 2005).

Limitations

Despite various interventions available, some limitations exist that hinder their efficiency. The cultural norms coupled with mental health-related stigma might prevent some women from seeking help or getting involved in treatments fully (WHO, 2021). Some cultures attach intense stigmatization to mental illnesses, which makes patients fear seeking professional guidance on this issue (Corrigan, 2014).

The effectiveness of many interventions is reduced because they are not specific to women. For instance, general therapeutic approaches are ineffective at addressing issues like reproductive healthcare, gender-based violence, and social and cultural aspects that affect women (WHO, 2019). Improving outcomes and ensuring women receive the required care necessitates developing culturally sensitive and gender-responsive interventions.

Discussions

Emotional disturbances have a significant impact on the social relationships and careers of women. Conditions such as

depression, anxiety, PTSD, and mood disorders have significant effects on different spheres of the lives of women, like romantic relationships with partners, parent-child interaction, and occupational environment, among others. To effectively deal with these problems, an integrated approach is called for, where psychotherapy should be combined with pharmacotherapy, in addition to community support services, while at the same time addressing sociocultural obstacles.

An all-inclusive treatment plan is vital to address multiple angles related to emotional disturbances. Amongst other modes, this is through psychotherapy, which includes cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT) or interpersonal therapy (IPT), which has proven efficient in improving emotional health and enhancing relationships (Cuijpers et al., 2016; Cuijpers et al., 2019). CBT helps identify and change negative thought patterns, whereas IPT concentrates on bettering one-on-one interactions coupled with communication abilities (Cuijpers et al., 2016). However, due to socioeconomic factors, the stigma attached to mental illness, and an inadequate number of trained personnel, it might only be possible for some females to access these therapies (Cuijpers et al., 2016; Olfson et al., 2017).

Pharmacotherapy, which encompasses antidepressants and anxiolytics, forms another important aspect of treatment. Although they can manage symptoms effectively, these drugs carry adverse effects that can undermine compliance levels and life quality (Gartlehner et al., 2017). By integrating pharmacotherapy with psychotherapy, a more holistic method can be employed to address symptomatic manifestations and the underlying psychosocial dimensions of emotional disturbances (Cuijpers et al., 2019).

Community-centered services such as peer support groups are crucial in the provision of emotional assistance and in minimizing loneliness (Kleiber & Lichtman, 2019). These groups enable women to share experiences and coping mechanisms, although they may not be sufficient for severe cases (Yalom & Leszcz, 2005). Addressing societal and cultural barriers is crucial for improving outcomes for women with emotional disturbances. Corrigan (2014) argues that stigma and cultural beliefs often prevent women from seeking help or fully participating in treatment. WHO (2021) also supports this view. In some cultures, mental health issues are stigmatized, which can prevent women from accessing necessary care (Corrigan, 2014). Additionally, gender-specific

stressors, such as societal expectations and gender-based violence, can exacerbate emotional disturbances and complicate treatment (Kuehner, 2017).

Improving access to care requires efforts aimed at reducing stigma and raising awareness about mental health. Public awareness campaigns on mental health could dispel misconceptions while emphasizing the need to seek professional help (Wang et al., 2007). Furthermore, culturally appropriate interventions that appreciate the unique challenges faced by women in different cultural contexts would enhance the efficacy of therapy or any other type of support rendered to them (WHO, 2019).

More research should be carried out to develop gender-based and culturally responsive interventions that deal with the peculiar hardships that women go through. It may well be worth conducting studies that assess the effectiveness of personalized interventions targeting specific cultural or social aspects, as it would help in improving the outcomes of treatment (Wang et al., 2007). Additionally, further exploration of integrated care models combining psychotherapy, pharmacotherapy, and community support may lead to improved management of

emotional disturbances in women (Cuijpers et al., 2019).

The role of societal factors such as socioeconomic status and cultural norms in shaping the experiences of women suffering from emotional disturbances is also an area for future research. These issues can guide the development of more targeted interventions and support systems that cater to diverse groups' needs (WHO, 2021).

Conclusion

This paper demonstrates how emotional disturbances like depression, anxiety, PTSD, and mood disorders affect different kinds of relationships among women, including romantic relationships, parent-child relationships, social relationships, and work-related relationships. These conditions negatively impact the psychological well-being of women, while their interpersonal interactions are strained with an overall detriment to their quality of life. This study highlights implications for a comprehensive approach toward addressing these concerns using medical, psychological, and social supports.

To better address both psychological symptoms as well as symptomatic aspects of mental health problems in women requires a combination of strategies,

including psychotherapies such as IPT or CBT, while medication can be used to manage symptoms to enhance overall treatment efficacy (Cuijpers et al., 2016; Gartlehner et al., 2017). Furthermore, incorporating peer support groups can assist in reducing isolation by providing shared coping mechanisms within such programs (Kleiber & Lichtman, 2019).

The review signifies the need to address societal and cultural barriers preventing women from seeking and receiving appropriate care. The stigma associated with mental illness or cultural norms deters women from seeking help, making emotional disturbances worse (Corrigan, 2014; WHO, 2021). Policymakers and healthcare providers should undertake public health campaigns and education to reduce stigma and create an environment that encourages women to seek help without concern for criticism.

The development of gender-sensitive and culturally responsive interventions is necessary for meeting the diverse needs of women with emotional disturbances. Therefore, research should focus on developing customized programs that consider culture, socioeconomic status, as well as individual factors (Wang et al., 2007). This means coming up with programs that deal specifically with

different problems faced by women in different societies across the globe while at the same time ensuring that all these interventions are accessible even to those who belong to low socioeconomic groups.

In conclusion, treating emotional disturbances among women needs a

comprehensive approach beyond just medicine, considering psychological matters together with social support. In addition, we can help women cope with their emotional problems and enhance their associations and well-being by integrating care services, reducing access barriers, and introducing focused interventions.

References

Albert, P. R. (2015). Why is depression more prevalent in women? *Journal of Psychiatry & Neuroscience*, 40(4), 219-221. <https://doi.org/10.1503/jpn.150205>

Baglioni, C., Battagliese, G., Feige, B., Spiegelhalder, K., Nissen, C., Voderholzer, U., ... & Riemann, D. (2011). Insomnia as a predictor of depression: A meta-analytic evaluation of longitudinal epidemiological studies. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 135(1-3), 10-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2011.01.011>

Bandelow, B., et al. (2017). Efficacy of drug treatments for anxiety disorders: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 20(5), 345-354.

Bauer, I. E., Sharma, V., & Mills, N. P. (2018). Bipolar disorder in women. In E. Vieta & J. Geddes (Eds.), *Bipolar II Disorder: Modelling, Measuring, and Managing* (pp. 167-182). Cambridge University Press.

Beesdo-Baum, K., Jenjahn, E., Höfler, M., Lueken, U., Becker, E. S., & Hoyer, J. (2012). Avoidant and dependent personality disorder in social anxiety disorder. *Depression and Anxiety*, 29(10), 916-923. <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.21972>

Cacioppo, J. T., Hughes, M. E., Waite, L. J., Hawkley, L. C., & Thisted, R. A. (2014). Loneliness as a specific risk factor for depressive symptoms: cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses. *Psychology and Aging*, 21(1), 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0882-7974.21.1.140>

Cacioppo, J. T., et al. (2014). Loneliness: clinical import and interventions. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 10(2), 238-249.

Cohen, S., & Wills, T. A. (1985). Stress, social support, and the buffering hypothesis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 98(2), 310-357. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.98.2.310>

Corrigan, P. W. (2014). How stigma interferes with mental health care. *American Psychologist*, 59(7), 614-625.

Corrigan, P. W. & Watson, A. C. (2002). Understanding the impact of stigma on people with mental illness. *World Psychiatry*, 1(1), 16-20.

Cuijpers, P., et al. (2016). Psychological treatment of depression in adults: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 202, 511-519.

Cuijpers, P., et al. (2019). The effects of psychotherapies for depression on the risk of suicide: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research*, 28(4), 1776.

Dworkin, E. R., et al. (2017). PTSD in the context of trauma-focused therapy: Impact on working alliance and therapy outcome. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 30(2), 156–165.

Dworkin, E. R., Menon, S. V., Bystrynski, J., & Allen, N. E. (2017). Sexual assault victimization and psychopathology: A review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 56, 65-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2017.06.002>

Eid, R. S., Chaaban, F., & Saliba, Y. (2019). Depression, anxiety, and labor: What are the associations? *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 19(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2234-7>

Field, T. (2010). Postpartum depression effects on early interactions, parenting, and safety practices: A review. *Infant Behavior and Development*, 33(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infbeh.2009.10.005>

Freeman, M. P., Smith, K., & Freeman, S. A. (2017). *Women's Mental Health Across the Lifespan*. Oxford University Press.

Gartlehner, G., et al. (2017). Comparative effectiveness of second-generation antidepressants for treating major depression: An updated meta-analysis. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 166(6), 493-503.

Ginsburg, G. S., Grover, R. L., & Ialongo, N. (2004). Parenting behaviors among anxious mothers: Relation with child anxiety and depressive symptoms. *Child & Family Behavior Therapy*, 26(4), 23–41. https://doi.org/10.1300/J019v26n04_02

Goodman, S. H., Rouse, M. H., Connell, A. M., Broth, M. R., Hall, C. M., & Heyward, D. (2011). Maternal depression and child psychopathology: A meta-analytic review. *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, 14(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10567-010-0080-1>

Greene, T., Gelkopf, M., Epskamp, S., & Fried, E. I. (2016). Dynamic networks of PTSD symptoms during conflict. *Psychological Medicine*, 46(7), 1525-1537. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291715002022>

Katon, W. J. (2011). Epidemiology and treatment of depression in patients with chronic medical illnesses. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 13(1), 7–23.

Kennedy, N., Boydell, J., Kalidindi, S., Fearon, P., Jones, P. B., & van Os, J. (2016). Gender differences in incidence and age at onset of mania and bipolar disorder over 35 years in Camberwell, England. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 162(2), 257–262. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.162.2.257>

Kessler, R. C., Ruscio, A. M., Shear, K., & Wittchen, H. U. (2008). Epidemiology of anxiety disorders. In M. B. Stein & T. Steckler (Eds.), *Behavioral neurobiology of anxiety and its treatment* (pp. 21-35). Springer.

Kleiber, D. A., & Lichtman, J. A. (2019). Support groups: a literature review and a proposal for future research. *Journal of Psychosocial Oncology*, 37(1), 30-44.

Kuehner, C. (2017). Why is depression more common among women than among men? *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 4(2), 146–158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30263-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30263-2)

Laxman, K. E., Lovibond, K. S., & Hassan, M. K. (2008). Impact of bipolar disorder in employed populations. *American Journal of Managed Care*, 14(11), 757-764.

Leahy, R. L., Holland, S. J., & McGinn, L. K. (2012). *Treatment Plans and Interventions for Depression and Anxiety Disorders*. Guilford Press.

- Leung, L., Chan, T., & Beiser, M. (2021). The psychological impact of social roles on women: A systematic review. *Journal of Clinical Psychology, 77*(8), 1765-1779. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.23053>
- Levy, B., & Johnson, M. A. (2014). Bipolar disorder and the family: effects and treatment. *Journal of Clinical Psychology, 70*(6), 531-544. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.22089>
- McLean, C. P., Asnaani, A., Litz, B. T., & Hofmann, S. G. (2011). Gender differences in anxiety disorders: prevalence, course of illness, comorbidity, and burden of illness. *Journal of Psychiatric Research, 45*(8), 1027-1035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2011.03.006>
- Mendlowicz, M. V., & Stein, M. B. (2000). Quality of life in individuals with anxiety disorders. *American Journal of Psychiatry, 157*(5), 669–682. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.157.5.669>
- Moak, Z. B., & Agrawal, A. (2010). Alcohol's effects on the brain: Mechanisms of addiction and mental health impacts. *Neuropsychology Review, 20*(3), 414-428.
- Muñoz, R. F., Cuijpers, P., Smit, F., Barrera, A. Z., & Leykin, Y. (2010). Prevention of major depression. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology, 6*(1), 181-212. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-033109-132040>
- Nolen-Hoeksema, S. (2012). Emotion regulation and psychopathology: The role of gender. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology, 8*, 161-187. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032511-143109>
- Perroud, N., et al. (2014). Predictors of response and remission in major depression: A prospective study in a naturalistic setting. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 163*, 123-129.
- Schnurr, P. P. & Green, B. L. (2004). Trauma and health: physical health consequences of exposure to extreme stress. *American Psychological Association*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10660-000>
- Simon, N. M. & Pollack, M. H. (2009). Anxiety disorders. *New England Journal of Medicine, 351*(13), 1257-1264.
- Stewart, D. E., & Vigod, S. N. (2016). Postpartum depression: pathophysiology, treatment, and emerging therapeutics. *Annual Review of Medicine, 67*(1), 231–243. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-med-050214-013524>

Stewart, D. E., & Vigod, S. N. (2019). *Women's Mental Health: A Clinical Guide* (3rd ed.). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-16166-0>

Weissman, M. M., Wickramaratne, P., Nomura, Y., Warner, V., Verdeli, H., & Pilowsky, D. (2006). Offspring of depressed parents: 20 years later. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 163(6), 1001-1008. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.2006.163.6.1001>

World Health Organization (WHO). (2017). *Depression and Other Common Mental Disorders: Global Health Estimates*. WHO Document Production Services.